

First data on the reproduction of Lanza's skink, *Chalcides lanzai* Pasteur, 1967

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INTRODUCTION

Although skinks of the genus *Chalcides* are fairly easy to keep and breed, there is relatively little interest in doing so by the general terrarium community. Of the about twenty known species, minimal data are published on keeping and breeding this genus in captivity. Most articles deal with *Chalcides ocellatus* (sold within in the pet trade), mostly originating from Egypt (see e.g. BOGAERTS, 1995; DAUT & ANDREWS, 1993; HARBIG, 1986; MUDDE & BAKKER-KAAGMAN, 1995; SCHLÜTER, 2006). Articles on other related species are rare; I am aware of only the following papers: *Chalcides bedriagai* (BOGAERTS, 1995), *Chalcides viridanus* (ALTMANN, 1985; IN DEN BOSCH, 1990); *Chalcides sexlineatus* (HARBIG, 2000), *Sphenops boulengeri* (HARBIG, 2001) and *Chalcides mionecton* (HARBIG, 2002).

To my knowledge, only a small number of people are seriously interested in keeping and breeding *Chalcides* species. These fascinating skinks are very secretive in the wild, which makes it difficult to observe

Moonlit habitat of *Chalcides lanzai*, September 2000.

Photo: David Donaire Barroso

Subadult *Chalcides lanzai*.

breeding habits and to collect field data, knowledge that can be gained more easily from keeping these animals in captivity.

Chalcides lanzai is listed by the IUCN (MIRAS et al., 2005) as Near Threatened because the extent of its occurrence is probably less than 5,000 km², thus making the species close to qualifying for Vulnerable. Major threats could be habitat loss and degradation of its habitat, which can be caused by expansion of agriculture or livestock. Presently its habitat does not appear to be significantly threatened.

ORIGIN AND DESCRIPTION

In September 2000, I received two subadult and one juvenile *Chalcides lanzai* collected that same month by David Donaire-Barroso in a *Cedrus atlantica* forest in the Middle Atlas, fairly near to Azrou, Morocco (N33°20'454"; W5°13'958", alt. 1823 m). He caught four skinks; one of which is preserved as a voucher specimen. In the same habitat he found *Bufo viridis*, *Podarcis vaucheri*, *Timon tingitanus*, *Acanthodactylus* cf. *belli*, *Coronella girondica*, and in the neighbourhood *Malpolon monspessulanus* also occurred. The *C. lanzai* turned out to be two males and one female.

In 1967 *Chalcides lanzai* was described as a subspecies of *Chalcides ocellatus* from the plateau de l'Agdal, Tioumliline (1850-1900 m), Middle Atlas, Morocco (PASTEUR,

Three specimens just after arrival; the largest one is a female, the other two are males (October 2000).

1967). At first sight the skink resembles *C. o. ocellatus*. CAPUTO & MELLADO (1992) gave it species rank. MATEO et al. (1995) supposed it might be a subspecies of *Chalcides montanus*, to which it is closely related. Like this form, it is also a high altitude species. *Chalcides montanus* and *C. lanzai* are found from 1257 m up to 2830 m, whereas *C. ocellatus* is found from sea level up to maximally 1700 m (BONS & GENIEZ, 1996).

Chalcides lanzai is a slender skink with relatively short limbs when compared to other species in the *Chalcides ocellatus* species group (MATEO et al., 1995). Typical features are the reddish-orange tail in juveniles, which turns orange pink in adults. Adults also have cream-yellowish coloured bellies.

METHODS

The animals were housed separately after arrival. Each vivarium had a surface area of about 45x25 cm, on which a layer of fine sand was deposited. The cage was further decorated with stones. A 25W spotlight provided heat and light. From mid-November until mid-March or even into April, the animals were placed together in a small vivarium filled with fine sand and a water bowl. At this point the animals hibernated by digging themselves in. The vivarium was put in the cellar where temperatures dropped to 5-10°C. After this period, the animals

were slowly prepared for spring by placing the terrarium at room temperature for a week, after which the animals were returned to their former vivariums. After a few weeks, one male was combined with the female. After about three months, the male was removed again and placed in its own cage. The animals were fed twice weekly with crickets and mealworms. The lizards also ate dead food items (dead crickets, tinned cat food). A bowl with water was always present and was refreshed every week.

RESULTS

Courtship behaviour was never observed. About six weeks prior to the birth of the juveniles (May 10, 2004; see photo), clear bite marks were noted on the neck of the female, an obvious sign that a mating had taken place.

Female *Chalcides lanzai* with bite mark (May 10, 2004).

Newly-born juvenile *Chalcides lanzai*.

On May 25, 2003 the first clutch of five juveniles was born. This was followed one year later by a clutch of six born on June 25, 2004, and then another eight on July 20, 2005 (measurements and weights are listed in Table I). Newly born juveniles have a bright orange tail. This colour fades, but leaves a pink-reddish coloration on the underside of the tail in adults. During growth, the belly gets more cream-yellowish in colour.

The juveniles born in 2003 were kept together as a group for the first two weeks. After this, they were isolated to make sure each animal got sufficient food. After three

25 May, 2003	SV (mm)	TL (mm)	Total (mm)	Weight (g)
1	40	35	75	1.3
2	41	37	78	1.2
3	41	34	75	1.4
4	41	35	76	1.3
5	41	37	78	1.2
Avg. 2003	40.8	35.6	76.4	1.28
25 June, 2004				
1	40	34	74	1.2
2	41	30	71	1.1
3	41	34	75	1.1
4	41	35	76	1.2
5	41	35	76	1.2
6*	41	35	75	1.0
Avg. 2004	40.8	33.8	74.5	1.13
20 July, 2005				
1	41	38	79	1.2
2	39	38	77	1.0
3	41	40	81	1.0
4	40	39	79	1.0
5	41	39	80	1.0
6	39	39	78	0.9
7	40	38	78	1.1
8	41	42	83	1.0
Avg. 2005	40.3	39.1	79.4	1.03
Total avg.	40.5	38.0	78.4	1.13

Table 1. Measurements on three clutches of newly-born juveniles of *Chalcides lanzai*. (SV = snout-vent length, TL = tail length)

*Survived with male and female for three days.

months (August 2003) the juveniles of the first clutch had reached, on average, a total length of 100 mm (snout-vent length [SV] 52 mm and tail length [TL] 48 mm) and weighed 2.1 g (n=5). October 2003, two animals were donated to Peter Harbig (Berlin). In January 2004 my three remaining animals had a length of 130 mm and an average weight of 4,8 g. They were not given a resting period in their first winter though their activity pattern clearly changed as they hardly showed themselves. From spring onwards the lizards were kept individually and were given a first hibernation 2004-2005. They were kept in the same way in the following years but were not measured. Of the second clutch, three lizards were given to Peter Harbig. The young of the third clutch, all still in my possession, were kept together until the time of writing. They were fed once a week. On August 25, 2006 they were measured and weighed (Table 2). The smallest animal measured 99 mm, the largest 138 mm. Weights were between 25-59 g. At that same time the adults and three 2003 subadults were measured (Table 3). One adult male and female are still alive (December 2006) but both show a regenerated

tail. The sizes mentioned in Table 3 are therefore a minimum total length for adult *C. lanzai*. The other (smaller) male of the original group died during the hibernation of 2005-2006.

DISCUSSION

Chalcides lanzai is as easy to keep and breed as the often-kept *C. ocellatus*. Clutch size seems to depend on the age of the female and can vary from five to eight juveniles, which is comparable to data on *Chalcides o. ocellatus* (SCHLÜTER, 2006). Interesting is that since the first birth in 2003, the moment of birth was about one month later each year. The longer hibernation periods, and consequently later mating, could be the cause of this. However, I did not note the exact times of these hibernation periods, although their duration varied by as much as a few weeks.

Two of the three animals received in September 2000 are still alive at the moment of writing (December 2006). When caught, the female was at least one year old. Therefore, *C. lanzai* can reach an age of at least six years. First reproduction was observed in 2003, which corresponds to the female

25 August, 2006	SV (mm)	TL (mm)	Total (mm)	Weight (g)	Remarks
	68	55	123	53	*
	72	66	138	59	
	52	59	111	32	
	54	45	99	29	**
	57	57	114	28	
	58	48	106	25	*
	61	61	122	29	
	60	46	106	30	*
Avg.	60.2	54.6	114.9	35.6	

Table 2. Measurements on 1 year old juveniles of *Chalcides lanzai*. (SV = snout-vent length, TL = tail length)

*Tip of the tail missing. **Left front leg missing.

25 August, 2006	SV (mm)	TL (mm)	Total (mm)	Weight (g)
Subadult	77	74	151	7.3
Subadult	87	81	168	9.2
Subadult	87	80	167	11.5
Male	102	76	178	18.3
Female	120	85	205	25.9

Table 3. Measurements taken on August, 2006 on adult and subadult (born in 2003) *Chalcides lanzai*. (SV = snout-vent length, TL = tail length)

Juvenile *Chalcides lanzai*, several weeks old.

being four years of age. Up until now she has produced three clutches (2003, 2004, and 2005). In 2006 there was no breeding because the sexes were housed separately.

Of the 13 museum specimens examined by CAPUTO & MELLADO (1992) the maximum SV was 104 mm. The female presented here has already reached 120 mm and the maximum total length in my sample is 21 cm (this animal has a regenerated tail). Adult *C. o. ocellatus* (from the Göksu Delta, Turkey) have an average SV of 84.8 mm and weigh on average 9.9 g (n=34) (VAN DER WINDEN & BOGAERTS, 1992). My two *C. lanzai* are longer, but also much heavier (18.3 and 25.9 g). The latter is probably due to terrarium feeding conditions since DAUT &

ANDREWS (1993) also give relatively high weights and lengths (22-39 g, SV 114-134 mm) for specimens in captivity.

The first, second and third clutch contained five, six and eight animals respectively. They had more or less the same lengths, but weight per juvenile was a little less in the largest clutch. Clutch sizes increase with adult size, as in other *Chalcides* species (HARBIG, 2002; SCHLÜTER, 2006).

Juveniles of *C. lanzai* seem to be a bit smaller than juveniles of *C. o. tiligugu* and *C. o. ocellatus*. However, they are bigger than *C. mionecton*. Juvenile *C. lanzai* are actually of roughly the same size as the smaller species, *C. sexlineatus*. Tables 4 and 5 present the underlying data for these statements.

Growth of the juveniles depends on the amount of food given. The first weeks I fed them twice a week, but later on this was modified to once a week. The growth rate in

a vivarium probably does not reflect growth in nature. *Chalcides o. tiligugu* born at the same moment as juveniles of *C. lanzai* in 2003 had grown just a little bit larger after three months (110 mm total length, and 2,8 g; n=2) under similar conditions.

One male of the original group died for unknown reasons while overwintering. No obvious illnesses were noted.

Competition over food leads to aggressive behaviour and causes large differences in growth between siblings, but it does not lead to major injuries – primarily the tip of the tail may be destroyed, although in one case a front leg was bitten off (see Table 2). Raising juveniles individually in separate tanks, as for *C. sexlineatus* (in HARBIG, 2000), is probably better but not absolutely necessary.

The single female reproduced for the first time at an age of four years. The young *C. lanzai* from 2003 have not reproduced yet,

Species	Clutch size	SV (mm)	Avg. weight g	Total (mm)	Reference
<i>C. bedriagai</i>	1-6	34-41	-	65	BOGAERTS, 1995; POLLO, 2003
<i>C. lanzai</i>	5-8	40.5	1.1	78.0	This paper
<i>C. mionecton</i>	1-5	37	0.5	72	Pers. unpubl. obs. (n= 3)
<i>C. mionecton</i>	1-5	37	-	62-74	HARBIG, 2002
<i>C. ocellatus ocellatus</i>	4-8	39-41	-	75-85; 80-88	HARBIG, 1986; SCHLÜTER, 2006
<i>C. ocellatus tiligugu</i>	8-12	-	-	81	SCHLÜTER, 2006
<i>C. ocellatus tiligugu</i>	5-10	42	1.2	81	Pers. unpubl. obs. (n=2)
<i>C. sexlineatus</i>	2-3	36.9	0.45	75-82	LÓPEZ-JURADO, 1998; HARBIG, 2000
<i>C. viridanus</i>	4	38-40	0.96	83-86	IN DEN BOSCH, 1990

Table 4. Clutch size, average length and weight of juvenile *Chalcides* species. (SV = snout-vent length)

Species	Maximum SV female (mm)	Reference
<i>C. bedriagai</i>	97.8	POLLO, 2003
<i>C. lanzai</i>	120	Pers. obs.
<i>C. mionecton</i>	107	HARBIG, 2002
<i>C. ocellatus tiligugu</i>	200	BONS & GENIEZ, 1996 ; SCHLÜTER, 2006
<i>C. ocellatus ocellatus</i>	143	SCHLÜTER, 2006
<i>C. sexlineatus</i>	93	HARBIG, 2000
<i>C. viridanus</i>	92	IN DEN BOSCH, 1990

Table 5. Maximal adult female snout-vent lengths in *Chalcides* species. (SV = snout-vent length)

neither with me nor with Harbig. Apparently, *C. lanzai* reaches reproductive adulthood after four years. This is relatively late compared to *C. ocellatus* (20 months, SV 90-95 mm: SCHLÜTER, 2006; two years: HARBIG, 1986), *C. sexlineatus* (24 months: HARBIG, 2000), or *C. mionecton* (three years; HARBIG, 2002). This could indicate a genetically fixed slow growth rate due to their life at a higher altitude with shorter seasons. But it could also be related to the conditions in captivity.

I hope this information will challenge people to study other *Chalcides* species to learn more about the ecology of this very diverse group of skinks.

Adult female and newly-born juvenile *Chalcides lanzai*.

SUMMARY

The first data on the reproduction of *Chalcides lanzai* are presented. One female and two males were kept in a vivarium. Data are given on the size of the clutches (5-8

young), lengths and weights of juveniles (on average a snout-vent length of 40.5 mm, tail length 38.0 mm, total length of 78.4 mm, and a weight of 1.13 g), and growth into adulthood. The female reproduced for the first time at an age of four years. These data are compared with data on other *Chalcides* species.

SAMENVATTING

In dit artikel zijn de eerste gegevens gepresenteerd over de voortplanting bij Lanza's skink, *Chalcides lanzai*. Een vrouwtje en twee mannetjes werden in een terrarium gehouden en er zijn gegevens genoteerd over de omvang van de worpen (5-8 jongen), lengten en gewichten van de jongen (gemiddelde kop-romplengte 40,5 mm, staartlengte 38,0 mm, totale lengte 78,4 mm, en een gewicht van 1,13 g), en over hun groei. Het vrouwtje bracht pas jongen ter wereld vanaf haar vierde jaar. Deze gegevens worden vergeleken met informatie over andere *Chalcidessoorten*.

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Male *Chalcides lanzai* (April 2004).

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